

Australia's Place in the World of Biodynamics

Dr John Paull

j.paull@utas.edu.au

Germany leads the world in certified biodynamic hectares, accounting for 34% of global certified biodynamic hectares (Paull & Hennig, 2020) (Fig. 1). Biodynamics began with a course of eight lectures by Rudolf Steiner in 1924 at Koberwitz, a village on the outskirts of Breslau, Germany (Steiner, 1924). The course was presented in German, and more than half of the 'Koberwitzers' were from Germany (Paull, 2020). The venue of the Agriculture Course survived Adolf Hitler's policy of 'Fortress Breslau' and the subsequent forfeiture of the region to the re nascent Poland (Paull, 2013a). The village is now Kobierzyce, on the outskirts of Wrocław, Poland.

Figure 1. World map of Biodynamic Agriculture (Source: (Paull & Hennig, 2020).

Australia is second in the world in certified biodynamic hectares, accounting for 20% of global certified biodynamic hectares (Paull & Hennig, 2020) (Fig.1). Australia was an early adopter of biodynamics. The AIF stretcher bearer and Italian immigrant, Ernesto Genoni, pioneered biodynamics in Australia. He joined Rudolf Steiner's Experimental Circle in

1928, the first Australian to join (Paull, 2013b). Ernesto Genoni spent 1924 at the headquarters of Anthroposophy in Dornach, Switzerland, attending Rudolf Steiner’s First Class, learning German in the process, and painting in the Anthroposophic style (Paull, 2014). Ernesto established the first biodynamic farm in Victoria, at Dalmore (Paull, 2019). With his partner, Ileen Macpherson, Ernesto Genoni operated Australia’s original Demeter Farm at Dandenong, Victoria, for two decades (Paull, 2017).

Table 1. Biodynamics in Europe: 20 countries account for 66% of global biodynamic hectares Data: Paull & Hennig, 2020; Jorry, 2020).

BD in Europe	BD hectares
Germany	84,426
France	14,629
Italy	10,781
Netherlands	8,681
Spain	7,743
Austria	7,164
Hungary	6,371
Switzerland	5,070
Poland	4,261
United Kingdom	3,886
Czech Republic	3,537
Denmark	2,998
Lithuania	1,389
Turkey	1,148
Sweden	873
Portugal	574
Norway	548
Luxembourg	536
Finland	384
Greece	381
TOTAL	165,380

Fifty five countries account for a global total of 251,842 certified biodynamic hectares. The global distribution is presented in the world map of biodynamics (Fig.1). The map is an area cartogram in which equal areas of the map account for equal areas of biodynamic hectares. To produce the map, territorial areas are evacuated (from a Peters-projection map of the world) and replaced by biodynamic areas (Paull & Hennig, 2020; Peters, 1983).

As the world map of biodynamics graphically reveals, Europe dominates the world of biodynamics. Twenty European countries account for 66% of global biodynamic hectares (Fig.1; Table 1).

Table 2. Biodynamics in English-speaking countries: 8 countries account for 29% of global biodynamic hectares (Data: Paull & Hennig, 2020; Jorry, 2020).

BD in the Anglosphere	BD hectares
Australia	49,797
India	9,303
United States	9,001
United Kingdom	3,886
New Zealand	928
Uganda	527
South Africa	245
Ireland	93
TOTAL	73,780

There was no Anglo presence at the Koberwitz course, and Rudolf Steiner never had the opportunity to repeat his Agriculture Course. Nevertheless, the diaspora of Anthroposophists, and the translation of the course into English by George Kaufmann (Adams), served to diffuse the ideas of biodynamics to the Anglosphere (Steiner, 1924). English speaking countries now account for 29% of global certified biodynamic hectares (Table 2).

References

- Jorry, A. (2020). personal communication: DI -Statistics-01-2020. Darmstadt: Demeter International.
- Paull, J. (2013a). Breslau (Wrocław): In the footsteps of Rudolf Steiner. *Journal of Biodynamics Tasmania*, 110(Winter), 10-15.
- Paull, J. (2013b). A history of the organic agriculture movement in Australia. In B. Mascitelli & A. Lobo (Eds.), *Organics in the Global Food Chain* (pp. 37-60). Ballarat: Connor Court Publishing.
- Paull, J. (2014). Ernesto Genoni: Australia's pioneer of biodynamic agriculture. *Journal of Organics*, 1(1), 57-81.

- Paul, J. (2017). Australia's original Demeter Farm (1934-1954). *Journal of Biodynamics Tasmania, September*(123), 16-19.
- Paul, J. (2019). Dalmore Farm: Victoria's first biodynamic farming venture (1933-1934). *Journal of Bio-Dynamics Tasmania, 131*, 26-31.
- Paul, J. (2020). The Koberwitzers: Those who attended Rudolf Steiner's Agriculture Course at Koberwitz in 1924, World's foundational organic agriculture course. *International Journal of Environmental Planning and Management, 6*(2), 47-54.
- Paul, J., & Hennig, B. (2020). A World Map of Biodynamic Agriculture. *Agricultural and Biological Sciences Journal, 6*(2), 114-119.
- Peters, A. (1983). *Die Neue Kartographie/The New Cartography*. (dual text: in German and English); Klagenfurt, Austria: Carinthia University; New York Friendship Press: Friendship Press.
- Steiner, R. (1924). *Agriculture Course* ("Printed for private circulation only"; 1929, first English language edition; George Kaufmann Trans ed.). Dornach, Switzerland: Goetheanum.